

NOTES

Complexes of Cu(II), Ni(II), Bi(III), Co(II), VO₂(II), Fe(III) and Pd(II) with 3-7 Dimethyl-7-Hydroxy-Octan-1-Al

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3-7 dimethyl-7-hydroxy-octan-1-al is an acyclic monoterpenoid. Having a hydroxyl and an aldehydic group, it shows great tendency towards complex formation. No work has been reported in literature on complex formation of this ligand with metal ions. The authors have reported¹⁻³ a number of complexes of this ligand with many metal ions. Present communication deals with the complex formation studies of 3-7 dimethyl-7-hydroxy-octan-1-al (commonly known as hydroxycitronellal) with metal ions like Cu(II), Ni(II), Bi(III), Co(II), VO₂(II), Fe(III) and Pd(II). 1 : 2 stoichiometry of the complexes, stability and thermodynamics of the complexes has been carried out by conductometric, pH metric, spectrophotometric studies, elemental analysis, infrared spectral measurements and magnetic susceptibility measurements.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of BDH AnalaR grade. 3-7 Dimethyl-7-hydroxy-octan-1-al (ligand for our purpose) procured from M/s H. Kelkar Co., Kerala, was purified by column chromatography and its purity was further checked on tlc plates.

Chlorides of copper, nickel, iron and palladium and nitrates of cobalt and bismuth were used. Vanadyl sulphate was used as such. A 0.01M standard stock solution of 3-7 dimethyl-7-hydroxy-octan-1-al was prepared in ethanol 0.001M stock solutions of metal salts were prepared in ethanol and doubly distilled water. Bismuth nitrate solution was prepared in HCl maintaining the pH-2 and finally making the solution upto mark with ethanol.

Toshniwal conductivity bridge model CLO1/02A with a dip type cell was used for conductometric measurements. pH metric titrations were carried out on an Elico pH meter model L1 - 10 using hydrogen and calomal electrodes. Spectrophotometric measurements were done on Bauch and Lomb's spectrophotometer of Spectronic-20. A Perkin Elmer

spectrophotometer model-621 was used for ir measurements. Magnetic measurements were performed on Gouy balance.

The Cu²⁺, Bi³⁺, Pd²⁺, Ni²⁺ and VO₂⁺ complexes were isolated in ethanolic media. Ethanolic solutions of metal salts and ligand were mixed in stoichiometric ratio (1 : 2) and stirred well. Solutions were refluxed for three hours and then isolated in different time intervals. Crystals were washed several times with ethanol and then dried over vacuo. Vanadyl complex was isolated in 50% ethanol-water media. All the complexes were microanalysed (Table 2).

Another interesting aspects was non-isolation of cobalt and iron complexes due to their more stability in solution than in solid. The non-isolation of these complexes was due to weak σ donor properties of the ligand.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes were found to have 1 : 2 ratio for metal to ligand. Reverse conductometric titrations⁸ and Job's continuous variation method⁴ were applied for conductance measurements. pH metric titrations were carried out in acetic acid -sodium acetate buffer media. Titration curves (not shown here) show the drop in pH and indicate the formation of metal ligand complexes⁵⁻⁶.

The metal salt solution are fairly acidic, initial drop in pH is not due to free metal ions, metal ions interact with the functional sites like -CHO groups, -OH group of the ligand liberating protons for which the initial pH drop is observed. Martell and Calvin⁷ pointed out that greater the tendency of metal to combine with a given chelating agent greater is the pH drop (Table 1).

TABLE 1—CONDUCTANCE, STABILITY AND OPTICAL DENSITY OF THE COMPLEXES

Metal salt used	Concentration	pH	Molar conductance	Log β	Optical density
CuCl ₂	0.01M to 0.005M	4.2	92.46	18.200	.33
NiCl ₂	0.01M to 0.005M	3.6	75.57	16.000	.24
Bi(NO ₃) ₃ .6H ₂ O	0.01M to 0.1M	3.5	82.00	17.383	.16
Co(NO ₃) ₂	0.01M to 0.005M	6.3	102.10	28.799	.41
VO ₂ SO ₄ .6H ₂ O	0.01M to 0.0025M	2.4	70.75	13.200	.30
FeCl ₃	0.01M to 0.005M	4.3	81.20	10.799	.16
PdCl ₂	0.01M to 0.005M	3.7	178.48	13.597	.41

TABLE 2—ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS AND IR DATA OF COMPLEXES

Complex	Media of isolation	% of Carbon		% of Hydrogen		% of Metal		Shifting of band in complex from ir band of ligand*
		Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	
Cu(C ₁₀ H ₁₉ O ₂) ₂	Ethanolic	54.35	54.32	8.60	8.41	14.39	14.50	-3700(s) ^φ -disappear [§]
Ni(C ₁₀ H ₁₉ O ₂) ₂	Ethanolic	54.95	54.86	8.70	8.69	13.44	13.21	3550wb disappear
Bi(C ₁₀ H ₁₉ O ₂) ₂ NO ₃ ·2H ₂ O	Ethanolic	39.03	38.43	6.00	6.00	32.96	32.85	3710ms disappear
VO ₂ (C ₁₀ H ₁₉ O ₂) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	Aqueous-Ethanolic	52.03	52.19	8.31	8.31	11.05	11.39	disappear
Pd(C ₁₀ H ₁₉ O ₂) ₂	-do-	51.49	51.62	8.21	8.21	22.75	22.61	disappear 1790wb

* ir band of ligand - band pertaining to ^φ-OH is 3600 cm⁻¹ ;
[§]-CHO is 1760 cm⁻¹.

Spectrophotometric studies were carried out by molar ratio method⁶ and Job's continuous variation method. The optical density fixed for complexes is shown in Table 1. The complexes obey Beer's law under the concentration range 1 × 10⁻³ M to 5 × 10⁻² M.

The ir spectra (Table 2) reveals that various bands assigned to the donor molecules of the ligand⁹ have shifted either to lower frequency region or higher frequency region. The shift of these bands show coordination of this ligand with metals. Elemental analysis of the complexes further confirms 1 : 2 stoichiometry of the ligand as well as structure of the complexes. The complexes are found to be insoluble in most of the common organic solvents like acetone, methanol, ether, benzene and chloroform etc. Their melting points are also given.

Thus from electrometric and analytical data complexes were found to have the following structure :

Here M = Cu²⁺, Ni²⁺, Bi³⁺, Co²⁺, VO₂³⁺ and Pd²⁺

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Mixed Ligand Anionic Complexes of Copper(II)

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STUDY of literatures reveals the preparation¹⁻⁷ of a large number of tetrahalo complexes of the type [L]₂[MX₄] where L = tetraalkylammonium halide or pseudo halide. Although, Bonamico and Dessy⁸ have synthesised anionic tetraalkylammonium tetrachloro cuprate(II) complexes which contain discrete distorted tetrahedral [CuCl₄]²⁻ ions, little

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